

USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract

The usage of various roles and games in foreign language instruction can help promote enthusiasm in language learning. Working in pairs or small groups allows students to communicate with one another. Within the approaches offered, role-playing, projects, and video scenarios can substantially broaden our creative horizons.

This article discusses different technologies in teaching English.

Keywords: interactive technologies, interactive learning, communicative competence, language skills, cooperative learning

The idea of interactive learning is that the learning process is designed such that practically all language learners are participating in the learning process. Cooperative actions of students in the process of learning educational content imply that each student makes their own unique differential contribution while information, ideas, and modes of activity are exchanged. Furthermore, this occurs in an environment of goodwill and mutual support, which enables not only for the acquisition of new knowledge, but also for the development of cognitive activity, bringing it to a higher level of cooperation and collaboration.

Massive information capabilities are currently made possible by the use of interactive learning technologies. These capabilities include organizational structures and ways to supply modern computer and information technology for use in the educational process. Information technology refers to the entirety of techniques and tools for gathering, arranging, storing, processing, transmitting, and presenting data in order to improve people's understanding and strengthen their capacity to oversee social and technological processes. Interactive technology is special because it allows one to build a true language environment in which language is used for its intended purpose, which is to construct and formulate ideas. It is an authentic learning setting with room for immersion in a foreign language and culture in addition to the problem. Students use virtual

libraries, databases, virtual cafés, virtual museums, and other information and instructional servers when they are searching for the correct information.

Due to the necessity of having real-time conversations with real people, students can communicate via email, websites designed especially for this purpose, etc. Simultaneously, the following learning objectives are typically noted for computer-based teaching aids: the individual's growth, readying them for a comfortable life in the information age; the growth of cognition, including visual-motor, visual-figurative, intuitive, creative, and theoretical forms of thought; aesthetic education, through the use of computer graphics and multimedia technologies; the development of communication skills, through forums, chats, and e-seminars; the development of decision-making abilities, through the use of computer games designed to optimize decision-making tasks; the formation of information culture, and the capacity for information processing.

This justifies the intensification of the educational process at all levels: the application of computer-assisted capability increases the effectiveness and quality of the learning process; incentives are offered that support the activation of cognitive activity (e.g., through computer visualization of educational information, blotches of game situations, management, mode selection of training activities). Accordingly, the following presumptions form the basis of the actual interactive learning technology usage model: A computer is only used for technical training when studying a foreign language; computers are frequently utilized in the classroom with a variety of student populations; teachers use computer training technology to the extent necessary to carry out the curriculum; as a result, firmware, educational tools do not need to abandon conventional teaching formats and techniques.

The discussion, opinion sharing, and arguing for and against the contentious issue are characteristics of interactive technologies. Any discussion-based session is more successful if the participants are familiar with the topic and the instructor has prepared the important ideas and points ahead of time. A teacher selects and formulates a topic, creates strategies for energizing and supervising participant participation, and schedules these steps during the planning phase. He needs to get ready the tools needed to capture the ideas of the students. The teacher acts as a mediator when the conversation gets going. It's critical to be able to discern several viewpoints on a given issue, form an opinion of one's own, draw conclusions, and assess accomplishments. You can introduce the topic to the audience in a number of ways, such as by describing a

difficult circumstance, posing problem questions, showcasing a video, acting out the scenario, or summarizing several viewpoints on the subject.

Diverse viewpoints should be included in a conversation so that the choice can ultimately be made. The project method is a series of investigations, data processing, and other tasks that students complete individually or in small groups in order to theoretically or practically solve a big problem. With project-based learning, the educational process is constructed via students' intentional engagement in line with their interests and objectives, which is a radically different approach. It is clear that the project method gives students the chance to express themselves, recognize their abilities, and plan out their future careers. Put another way, the learner is given the chance to focus on his interests, capabilities, and abilities while also attempting to test himself in many areas and disclose something personal and fascinating.

Most significantly, all of his actions are directed toward the development of his own, experience-based way of thinking. He is equally accountable for his own growth and degree of preparation for future self-employment. Using a wide range of research techniques is fundamental to project-based learning. These techniques are important for the student as well as for the problem's holistic development, which takes into account a number of variables and conditions for the problem's solution and results' implementation. The main reason project-based learning has become so popular worldwide is that it makes it easy to combine students' knowledge from various subjects to solve problems, enables them to put their knowledge into practice, and fosters the generation of new ideas all at once. As previously said, there is a fundamental issue with the project. Students must have a great degree of topic knowledge that is both sufficient and required to answer the challenge in addition to language proficiency in order to solve it. Students also need to have a certain set of creative, intellectual, and communication skills.

These include the capacity to deal with data, with a text (highlight the primary concept, locate pertinent information in a text written in a foreign language), to analyze data, draw conclusions, draw generalizations, etc., and the capacity to work with a range of reference materials. The purpose of teaching various speech activity kinds is to help students develop these skills.

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